

OPERATIONAL AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF URBAN COOPERATIVE BANKS IN INDIA

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Abstract

This study attempts to measure the operational and financial performance of Urban Cooperative Banks in India. Analytical frame of the operational tools in terms of the Credit Deposit Ratio and Investment Deposit Ratio, and to different financial segments, purposes; and also, the trends over the period under study have been presented. The study is based on secondary data collected from annual reports of urban cooperative banks in India for the study period i.e. 2005-06 to 2015-16. Ratios are used here with financial ratio analysis (FRA) method which helps to draw an overview about financial performance of the urban cooperative banks in terms of profitability, liquidity and credit performance. To test the hypothesis the study has been worked on Statistical tools correlation, t-test by using SPSS. These analyses are helps to see the current performance condition of these urban banks to compare past performance. The study findings can be helpful for management of urban cooperative banks. The study also identified specific areas for urban cooperative banks to work on which can ensure sustainable growth and development for these scheduled banks and non-scheduled banks.

Key words: Operational Performance, Profitability, Financial ratio analysis, Credit Deposits Ratio and Investment Ratio.

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1. Introduction

The operational performance of the urban cooperative banks depends on the flow of funds in the form of mobilization of deposits, creation of reserves and borrowings on one side, and deployment of credit, effective recovery of loans lent, prudential norms in management of non-performing assets and managerial efficiency on the other. The Cooperative Planning Committee felt this: “Urban cooperative banks qualify by establishing personal and intimate relationship with the people of urban class as the most suitable agencies for servicing for their credit needs. The urban cooperative banks on the principle of cooperation is ‘discrimination to none and open to all.’ The operational performance of the sample urban cooperative banks in terms of flow of funds is examined diligently in this chapter with regards to the sources of funds and deployment of funds, recovery of loans lent and non-performing assets including the managerial efficiency.

The most common measure of bank performance is profitability. Generally, accounting profits are the difference between revenues and costs. Profitability is considered to be the most difficult attributes of a firm to conceptualize and to measure (Ross, Westerfield, and Jaffe 2005). These ratios are used to assess the ability of the business to generate earnings in comparison with its all expenses and other relevant costs during a specific time period. More specifically, these ratios indicate firm’s profitability after taking account of all expenses and income taxes, the efficiency of operations, firm pricing policies, profitability on assets and to shareholders of the firm (Van Horne 2005). Profitability ratios are generally considered to be the basic bank financial ratio in order to evaluate how well bank is performing in terms of profit. For the most part, if a profitability ratio is relatively higher as compared to the competitor(s), industry averages, guidelines, or previous years’ same ratios, then it is taken as indicator of better performance of the bank. Study applies these criteria to judge the profitability of the National banks Limited.

Profitability is measured using the following criteria Profitability is an important to evaluate the overall efficiency of a bank's fund management. The term profitability can be defined as an ability to earn profit and is measured in relative terms. Profitability in banking denotes the efficiency with which a bank deploys its total resources to optimize managerial effectiveness (Singh and Singh 2006). Profitability is an index of operational efficiency of banks their performance among others is gauged on this important parameter. (Kohli and Chawla 2006). In order to evaluate the profit and profitability performance in India, the following indicators have been used.

2. Literature Review

Sanjeev Kumar (2013), the importance of this study the private sector banks operating in India by using operating and financial ratios. They analysed the asset qualities has an unpremeditated strategy for new private sector banks operating in India. It has also been found that New Private Sector Banks enhanced the importance of priority sector lending into by taking advantages of the present provisions.

Anurag (2012), the objective of the study is to examine the financial performance of ICICI and SBI Bank, public sector and private sector respectively. The data used for the study was entirely secondary in nature. The present study is conducted to compare the financial performance of SBI and ICICI Bank on the basis of ratios such as credit deposit, net profit margin etc.

M. Kavitha (2012), the major objective of the study is to analyse the financial performance of the selected public sector banks. Financial performance of the selected public sector banks were analysed for the period of ten years with the considering the following tools and techniques, Ratio Analysis, Correlation, Regression. The result reveals that public sector banks have performed well on the sources of growth rate and financial efficiency during the study period. The old private sector banks and new private sector banks play a vital role in marketing of new type of deposits and advances schemes.

3. Research Objectives

Main objectives of the study is as follows

- ❖ To study and analyze the financial performance of Urban Cooperative Banks in India.
- ❖ To know the Operational Performance of Urban Cooperative Banks in India.
- ❖ To understand the profitability of Urban Cooperative Banks in India.

4. Research Hypotheses

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypotheses are to be tested:

- ❖ There is no significance association of operational performance in between Scheduled banks and Non-scheduled banks of urban cooperative banks.
- ❖ There is no significance association of financial performance in between Scheduled banks and Non-scheduled banks of urban cooperative banks.

5. Methodology

Data and methodology

Collection of Data and Its Analysis Method: The present study is based on the secondary Data extracted from the annual reports of Urban Cooperative Bank Limited over a period of 2006-07 to 2015-16, from which financial structure of the Banks have been taken. The collected data was analyzed by using statistical tools and techniques namely Correlation and T test Analysis. In order to get the results, statistical software such as MS- Excel and SPSS has been used. Charts and Figures had been prepared for presenting and simplifying the process of analysis. Performance indicators are

classified in two .e. operational performance and financial performance indicators these are the explanatory variables represented here under

Table-1		
Operational Performance Indicators		
Type of variable	Proxy	Sign
Borrowings Ratio	Borrowings/Number of Banks	BOR
Total Business Ratio	Total Business/Number of Banks	TBR
Investments Ratio	Investments/Number of Banks	INVR
Owned Funds Ratio	Owned Funds/Number of Banks	OFR
Credit Deposit Ratio	Loans & Advances/Deposits	CDR

Table-2		
Financial Performance Indicators		
Type of variable	Proxy	Sign
Operating Ratio	Operating Cost/Total Income	OCR
Net Profit Ratio	Net Profit/Total Income	NPR
Return on Deposits Ratio	PAT/ Deposits	RDR
Return on Equity Ratio	PAT/Equity	RER
Return on Borrowings Ratio	PAT/Borrowings	RBR

ANALYSIS OF STUDY

Table 3: Size of Urban Co Operative Banks in India

Year	Scheduled Co-operative Urban Banks	Non Scheduled Co operative Urban Banks	Total UCBs
2005-06	55	1798	1853
2006-07	53	1760	1813
2007-08	53	1717	1770
2008-09	53	1668	1721
2009-10	53	1621	1674
2010-11	53	1592	1645
2011-12	52	1566	1618
2012-13	51	1555	1606
2013-14	51	1538	1589
2014-15	50	1529	1579
Mean	53	1613	1687
Range	5	269	274
SD	1.47	93.31	97.75

Source: Compiled from RBI reports on trend and progress of banking in India:
relevant issues

Table 3: reveals the growth of banks after vision document of the RBI in scheduled and non-scheduled urban cooperative banks. The scheduled banks have declined from the year 2006-07 is 55 to 50 banks in the year 2015-16. And the same manner non- scheduled urban cooperative banks have declined from the year 2006-07 is 1,798 to 1,529 banks in the 2015-16. The Reserve Bank of India adopted a multi – layered regulatory and supervisory strategy aimed at the merger/ amalgamation of viable UCBs and the exit of unviable ones for the revival of this sector. This initiative led to a gradual reduction in the number of UCBs. As a result total number of UCBs at the end of March 2015 stood at 1,579 against 1,853 in the year 2005-06.

Table-4							
Scheduled Banks							
YEAR	Borrowings Ratio	Total Business Ratio	Investments Ratio	Owned Funds Ratio	Credit Deposit Ratio	Total Score	Altimate Rank
2006-07	16.76 (10)	1332 (10)	410.78 (10)	115.24 (10)	0.62 (8)	48	1
2007-08	25.35 (8)	1584.5 (8)	431.55 (9)	148.92 (9)	0.64 (5)	39	2
2008-09	27.85 (7)	1792.8 (7)	486.34 (8)	152.4 (7)	0.61 (9.5)	38.5	3.5
2009-10	21.53 (9)	2022.9 (6)	502.4 (7)	201.9 (7)	0.61 (9.5)	38.5	3.5
2010-11	33.64 (6)	1576.6 (9)	586.92 (6)	226.2 (6)	0.63 (7)	34	5
2011-12	52.83 (1)	2905.7 (5)	632.07 (5)	247.2 (5)	0.67 (2)	18	6
2012-13	40.38 (3)	2971 (4)	711.54 (4)	286.65 (2)	0.67 (2)	15	7
2013-14	36.82 (5)	4121.7 (3)	890.41 (3)	248.67 (4)	0.67 (2)	17	8
2014-15	41.7 (2)	4694.8 (2)	948.92 (2)	281.92 (3)	0.64 (5)	14	9
2015-16	38.02 (4)	5399.8 (1)	1031.14 (1)	324.56 (1)	0.64 (5)	12	10
Mean	33.48	2840	6632	223.37	0.64	-	-
Range	36.02	4067.8	620	209	0.06	-	-
SD	10.75	1448	224	68	0.024	-	-

Source: Computed from RBI reports on trend and progress of banking in India: Bracket values indicated that computed Ranks

It can be seen from above table all the performance ratios of scheduled banks have been progressive from year 2005-06 to 2015-16. Three ratios have ranked first, borrowings ratio has fourth rank and CDR has fifth rank in the year 2015-16. Out of five ratios; Total business ratio has highest range and SD.

Table-5							
Non- Scheduled Banks							
YEAR	Borrowings Ratio	Total Business Ratio	Investments Ratio	Owned Funds Ratio	Credit Deposit Ratio	Total Score	Altimate Rank
2006-07	0.48 (6)	62.54 (10)	15.46 (10)	4.25 (10)	0.64 (4)	40	1
2007-08	0.74 (3)	66.56 (9)	15.90 (9)	5.86 (9)	0.67 (1)	31	4
2008-09	0.70 (4)	78.8 (8)	18.13 (8)	7.00 (8)	0.67 (1)	29	5
2009-10	0.03 (10)	87.56 (7)	23.07 (7)	9.25 (7)	0.62 (7)	38	2
2010-11	0.34 (7)	101.6 (6)	29.65 (6)	11.17 (6)	0.60 (10)	35	3
2011-12	1.01 (1)	122.05 (5)	32.41 (5)	12.25 (5)	0.63 (6)	22	6.5
2012-13	0.95 (2)	135.12 (4)	32.56 (4)	12.32 (3)	0.65 (3)	16	10
2013-14	0.52 (5)	159.26 (3)	40.58 (3)	13.54 (2)	0.64 (4)	17	9
2014-15	0.28 (8)	181.2 (2)	43.50 (2)	12.32 (3)	0.62 (7)	22	6.5
2015-16	0.22 (9)	202.4 (1)	46.82 (1)	13.8 (1)	0.62 (7)	19	8
Mean	0.52	1197	29.81	10.17	0.63	-	-
Range	0.98	139.8	31.36	9.55	0.07	-	-
SD	0.32	48.94	11.49	3.39	0.22	-	-

Source: Computed from RBI reports on trend and progress of banking in India: Bracket values indicated that computed Ranks

It can be seen from above table all the performance ratios of non-scheduled banks have fluctuate from year 2005-06 to 2015-16. Three ratios have ranked first, borrowings ratio has ninth rank and CDR has seventh rank in the year 2015-16. Out of five ratios; Total business ratio has highest range and SD.

Table-6 Scheduled Banks							
YEAR	Operating Profit Ratio	Net Profit Ratio	Return on Deposits Ratio	Return on Equity Ratio	Return on Borrowings Ratio	Total Score	Altimate Rank
2006-07	0.12 (2)	0.06 (9)	0.005 (9)	0.21 (10)	0.27 (9)	39	2
2007-08	0.13 (1)	0.11 (3)	0.01 (2)	0.41 (6)	0.38 (7)	19	7.5
2008-09	0.11 (5)	0.10 (6)	0.008 (6)	0.38 (8)	0.34 (8)	33	3
2009-10	0.12 (2)	0.14 (1)	0.013 (1)	0.64 (1)	0.79 (1)	6	10
2010-11	0.11 (5)	0.11 (3)	0.01 (2)	0.53 (3)	0.48 (6)	19	7.5
2011-12	0.09 (7)	0.06 (9)	0.005 (9)	0.29 (9)	0.19 (10)	44	1
2012-13	0.09 (7)	0.12 (2)	0.01 (2)	0.52 (4)	0.57 (4)	19	7.5
2013-14	0.08 (10)	0.11 (3)	0.01 (2)	0.56 (2)	0.74 (2)	19	7.5
2014-15	0.12 (2)	0.07 (7)	0.008 (6)	0.42 (5)	0.55 (5)	25	5
2015-16	0.09 (7)	0.07 (7)	0.007 (8)	0.40 (7)	0.64 (3)	32	4
Mean	0.10	0.09	0.008	0.44	0.45	-	-
Range	0.05	0.08	0.01	0.43	0.79	-	-
SD	0.017	0.03	0.002	3.39	0.25	-	-

Source: Computed from RBI reports on trend and progress of banking in India: Bracket values indicated that computed Ranks

It can be seen from above table all the financial ratios of scheduled banks have been fluctuate trend from year 2005-06 to 2015-16. Operating ratio, NP ratio and ROE have ranked seventh, Return on Deposit ratio has eight rank and Return on Borrowings has third rank in the year 2015-16. Out of five ratios; Return on Equity ratio has highest range and SD.

Table-7
Non- Scheduled Banks

YEAR	Operating Profit Ratio	Net Profit Ratio	Return on Deposits Ratio	Return on Equity Ratio	Return on BorrowingsRatio	Total Score	Altimate Rank
2006-07	0.04 (6)	0.04 (10)	0.001 (10)	0.04 (9)	0.13 (10)	45	1
2007-08	0.04 (6)	0.09 (1)	0.004 (9)	0.10 (8)	0.22 (9)	33	2.5
2008-09	0.06 (3)	0.08 (2)	0.008 (4)	0.19 (3)	0.55 (7)	19	7
2009-10	0.08 (1)	0.06 (6)	0.006 (6)	0.16 (6)	1.08 (5)	24	5
2010-11	0.07 (2)	0.06 (6)	0.006 (6)	0.17 (5)	1.25 (4)	23	6
2011-12	0.05 (5)	0.06 (6)	0.005 (8)	0.16 (6)	0.44 (8)	33	2.5
2012-13	0.04 (6)	0.08 (2)	0.007 (5)	0.002 (10)	0.66 (6)	29	4
2013-14	0.06 (3)	0.08 (2)	0.009 (2)	0.25 (1)	1.73 (3)	11	10
2014-15	0.04 (6)	0.06 (6)	0.07 (1)	0.20 (2)	2.95 (2)	17	8
2015-16	0.04 (6)	0.08 (2)	0.009 (2)	0.19 (3)	5.11 (1)	14	9
Mean	0.052	0.06	0.125	0.54	1.41	-	-
Range	0.04	0.09	0.07	0.40	4.98	-	-
SD	0.015	0.03	0.020	1.60	1.54	-	-

Source: Computed from RBI reports on trend and progress of banking in India: Bracket values indicated that computed Ranks

It can be seen from above table all the financial ratios of non-scheduled banks have been fluctuate trend from year 2005-06 to 2015-16. NP ratio and ROD have ranked second, Return on Equity ratio has third rank, Operating Profit ratio and Return on

Borrowings has first rank in the year 2015-16. Out of five ratios; Return on Borrowings ratio has highest range and SD.

Testing of Hypotheses Correlation Analysis

Correlation is concern describing the strength of relationship between two variables. In this study the correlation co-efficient analysis is undertaken to find out the relationship between operational performance and financial performance of Urban Cooperative Banks comprising of Scheduled and Non- scheduled banks in India. The measure of correlation is called the co-efficient of correlation. It is denoted by 'r' and the simplest formula for computing the appropriate **t value** to test significance of a correlation coefficient employs the t distribution.

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

The **degrees of freedom** for entering the t-distribution is **N – 2**. Table value of(10-2) i.e. 8 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 2.306 for two tailed test.

Rank Correlation between Operational Performance and Financial performance of Urban Co-operative Banks

Table-8

Year	OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE		FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE	
	Scheduled Banks R ₁	Non-Scheduled Banks R ₂	Scheduled Banks R ₁	Non-Scheduled Banks R ₂
2006-07	1	1	2	1
2007-08	2	4	7.5	2.5
2008-09	3.5	5	3	7
2009-10	3.5	2	10	5
2010-11	5	3	7.5	6
2011-12	6	6.5	1	2.5
2012-13	7	10	7.5	4
2013-14	8	9	7.5	10
2014-15	9	6.5	5	8
2015-16	10	8	4	9
r- value	0.80		0.22	
Significant value	.006		0.536	
t-value of r	2.83		0.64	
Hypotheses Result	Hypothesis (H₁): Rejected		Hypothesis (H₂): Accepted	

Sources: Calculations are done using SPSS

Correlation of operational performance of the urban co-operative banks in between scheduled banks and non-scheduled banks is high positive correlation and its relationship strength is 0.64 or 64 per cent and significant. Its correlation t- value is 2.83, here given hypothesis one is rejected. Further it is concluded that operational performance of the urban co-operative banks in between scheduled banks and non- scheduled banks is not similar and operational activities are different.

While comparing financial performance of these scheduled banks and non-scheduled banks has low positive correlation and its relationship strength is 0.044 or 4.4 per cent. Calculated t-value is 0.64, which is compared to the critical table value, calculated value is low. Where given hypothesis two is accepted and insignificant relation as per statistical results. Therefore, it is concluded that profitability performance point of view there is no difference of operations in between the scheduled banks and non-scheduled banks of urban co-operative banks in India.

Observations and Conclusion

This study presents the major findings of the operational and financial performance of Urban Co-operative Banks in India over a period of ten years from 2005-2006 to 2015-2016. The Study was done the following observations, which are discussed here under.

- It is observed that operational performance of the scheduled banks is progressive, whereas, nonscheduled banks are in fluctuating during the study period.
- Total business of the scheduled and non-scheduled banks was taken high risk and volume of business was also high range during last 10 years
- Credit Deposit Ratio is all most similar in between scheduled bank and nonscheduled banks during the study period.
- Borrowings point of view scheduled banks have high level of risk as compared to the non-scheduled banks.
- It is observed that urban cooperative banks have made high volume of investments through scheduled bank and non-scheduled banks.

- It is found that financial performance point view both scheduled and non- scheduled banks have same level probability seen during the study period.
- Returns on Borrowings of the urban cooperative banks have been taken high level of risk.

Urban co-operative banks financial performance is similar level with scheduled banks and nonscheduled banks. Whereas, operational performance scheduled banks performance are better as compared to non-scheduled banks during the study period. Central Government and Reserve Bank of India should give encouragement and financial support and assistance for better development of urban cooperative banks and improve its services public at large. It is suggested that urban co-operative banks should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets, borrowings, deposits, debt and improving the productive efficiency of employees. Profitability of the investments and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved efficiency. In addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction costs and management of funds are very much influenced to the corporation for better performance.

References

Avkiran, N.K., Cai, L. (2012) Predicting bank financial distress prior to crises, UQ Business School, The University of Queensland, Australia, Working paper. Available at <http://www.nzfc.ac.nz/archives/2012/papers/updated/24.pdf>

Derviz, A. and J. Podpiera, (2008) Predicting Bank CAMELS and S&P Ratings: The Case of the Czech Republic, *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, vol. 44, no. 1, p. 117-130.

Evan, O. et al. (2000) Macroprudential Indicators of Financial System Soundness, *IMF Occasional Paper*, no. 192.

Gunsel, N. (2007) Financial Ratios and the Probabilistic Prediction of Bank Failure in North Cyprus, *European Journal of Scientific Research*, vol.18, no.2, p.191-200.

Hays, F., De Lurgio, S. and A., Jr., Gilbert (2009) Efficiency Ratios and Community Bank Performance, *Journal of Finance and Accountancy*, vol. 1, no. 1. IMF and World Bank (2005) *Financial Sector Assessment: A Handbook*.

Mensi, S. and A., Zouari (2010) Efficient Structure versus Market Power: Theories and Empirical Evidence, *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 2 (4), p. 151-166.

Mishra, A. K., Harsha, G. S., Anand, S. and N. R., Dhruva (2012) Analyzing Soundness in Indian Banking:, *Research Journal of Management Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 3.

Molyneux, P. and Seth, R. (1998) Foreign banks, profits and commercial credit extension in the United States, *Applied Financial Economics*, 8, p. 533-539.

Annual Reports of urban co-operative banks 2005-2016. RBI Reports

Finance Management and policy –Bhalla, V.K; Amol publications Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi – 110 002.

Financial Hand book –Joles I.Bogan.

Financial Management and policy; J.C Ven Horne; prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.

Khan M.Y. and P.K Jain., *Financial Management - Text and Problems*, Tata Mc Graw Hill publications, New Delhi.

Prasanna Chandra, *Financial Management- Theory and practice*, publications, Tata Mc Graw Hill publications, New Delhi.